

SMALL HYDROELECTRIC POWER PLANT, INTEGRALY CONTROLLED BY CALCULATION TECHNIQUE**Cristian Purece,***PhD in hydropower,**Scientific Secretary at INCDIE ICPE-CA Bucharest Subunit ICEMENERG
Bd. Energeticienilor, no.8, Sctor 3, Bucharest, Romania***Dorian Marin***PhD in electric engineering**Scientific Researcher II at INCDIE ICPE-CA Bucharest Subunit ICEMENERG
Splaiul Unirii, no. 313, Sector 3, Bucharest, Romania***Abstract**

The good operation of the automation systems with which the small hydropower plants are equipped has an important contribution to the optimal operation of these small hydropower plants. Outdated, inefficient automation must be replaced with modern, computer-based control in order to obtain the best possible efficiency. Such a modernized automatic control system was implemented at the small hydropower plant Leșu. The automatic control and command system fully ensures monitoring and automatic commands for the efficient and safe operation of the hydropower plant, including in failure conditions. The supervision and control of the plant's operations is done centrally, from the hydropower plant's control room through the automation system.

Keywords: hydropower plants, control system, automation, turbine

Introduction

In Romania, there are currently 528 small hydropower plants (SHHP) with powers below 4 MW, with a total installed capacity of 468.6 MW. Although these hydropower plants have small powers, they are practically equipped with the same installations and equipment as large hydropower plants [1].

These SHPP are provided with automatic voltage and speed control, with oil pressure groups, exhaust installations and with installations for the provision of own services, necessary for a good operation of the plant.

The automation systems that now equip the SHHP in Romania are totally outdated from a moral and physical point of view, and have a high degree of physical wear and tear.

Due to the previously mentioned, the operation of these SHHP is controlled manually, with low efficiency and with an exaggerated consumption of water and human resources, and the yield of SHHP is low.

The apparition on the market of the electronic automation equipment, destined to the industrial technological processes, made possible an integral control system for the small hydropower to be achieved [2]. Such a system was achieved and implemented by

ICEMENERG in cooperation with the customer at the HPP Leșu.

Location

The reservoir of SHPP Leșu has a volume of 28.4 million cubic meters. The dam is built of rocks and its height is 60 m.

The hydro aggregate that equips SHPP Leșu is of the vertical, synchronous type. The turbine is of type Francis with a steel spiral casing and has a discharge (Q) of 8 mc/s and a nominal power (P) of 3.4 MW. The exciter and the top cover of the generator are on the ground surface; the protection against the external environment is achieved by means of a steel casing. The technological installations are installed underground and the electrical control and automation installations are installed in above-ground rooms.

The electrical diagram in which the hydrogen generator works is simple. A step-up transformer, 6.3 MVA, 6.3/20 kV, which allows energy to be discharged into the local network. Link with the local network is made through two 20 kV overhead power lines. Own services are provided both from the hydrogenerator terminals through a 6.3/0.4 kV voltage step-down transformer, as well as from the local network, through a 20/0.4 kV transformer (Figure 1).

- the automation system (secondary part) that drives the trial.

In general, the reliability of the technological process is determined by the reliability of each of the previously presented components.

It can be stated that, in the last period, the primary part has not undergone significant, major technological developments and in most hydropower plants in Romania it is still in an acceptable / good state of operation. It is mainly about the hydraulic turbine, hydrogen generator, valves, electrical equipment, but also the actual hydropower installation.

But the situation of the secondary part, of the automation systems, is completely different. The classic solution, based on the use of electromagnetic relays, is totally outdated from a technical point of view. But because with the passage of time, physical wear also intervened, automation systems became a main risk factor in the operation of hydropower plants, being one of the important causes of reducing their availability.

At SHHP Leșu, using relatively small financial resources, the automation installations could be modernized, the effect being the significant increase in the performance of the entire plant.

At present, modern technique and technology provide us with several solutions for the realization of hydropower control systems [5]. They are based on state-of-the-art achievements in the field of microprocessors, computing technology in general.

Regardless of the adopted solution, modern systems of management of hydropower plants must ensure at least the following facilities:

- to have a very good reliability;
- to perform at least the classical automation functions;
- to have a good immunity to electromagnetic disturbances
- powerful from hydropower plants;
- to be resistant to climatic demands (temperature, moisture);
- to allow the implementation of optimization functions a hydropower plant operation depending on the head and discharge;
- to allow the realization of new functions that automatic classical cannot provide them;

- to be able to ensure the connection with a computing device of a higher hierarchical level;

- to be understood by the operating staff.

It should be mentioned that a modern control system requires the installation of high-performance transducers. Classic systems, using detection elements, can no longer satisfy the current requirements.

A control system based on a single programmable controller was implemented at CHE Leșu.

Automation implemented at HPP Leșu

The works carried out at the SHPP Leșu aimed at the implementation of the following equipment:

- the central computer cabinet;
- the central computer;
- specialized transducers of hydromechanical quantities (pressures, flows, levels, displacements);
- specialized transducers of electrical quantities, respectively smart electrical meters.

The programmable controller (PLC) and the power sources of the automation equipment were mounted in the central computer cabinet. For safety reasons, the supply is made with 220 V direct current, from the power plant's battery.

Control system implemented at HPP Leșu

The management system implemented at SHPP Leșu was realized in a centralized concept.

It is made up of a programmable automaton and a central computer located in the control room (Figure 2).

The programmable automaton installed at CHE Leșu ensures the following facilities:

- orders and supervises the fulfillment of the conditions of starting;
- commands and supervises starting, stopping, respectively stopping automatic failure of the hydraulic system;
- commands and supervises the automatic operation of own service installations of the power plant and the hydro aggregate;
- measures and records the operating time of the important primary equipment of the plant;
- orders and supervises the fulfillment of the conditions of operation.

Fig. 2. The structure of control system implemented at CHE Leșu [3]

To undertake the informations from the HPP, the programmable controller is connected with some specialized transducers.

The measured parameters are as follows:

- cooling water flows and turbined flow;
- temperatures in 22 measuring points (bearings and the generator stator);
- water and oil levels;
- water, oil and air pressures;
- regulation elements displacement;
- generator speed.

In order to monitor electricity, three smart electricity meters were installed, at the following measuring points:

- generator terminals;
- LEA 20 kV overhead power line, Remeti;
- LEA 20 kV overhead power line, Ponoare.

For each measurement point, the following parameters will be measured:

- active powers per phase, their meaning and sum;
- reactive powers per phase, their meaning and sum;
- phase and line voltages and their averages;
- phase currents and their averages;
- active energy delivered and consumed;
- reactive energy delivered and consumed;

- power factor and frequency.

The programmable automaton works autonomously. Loading the discharge with / of power is done by the operating staff, with the help of the buttons mounted on the panels.

Another important component of the control system is the central computer in the control room of the hydropower plant.

The calculator has two main functions:

- supervising the operation of the hydro unit, respectively alarming the staff when prescribed limits are exceeded

of the technological parameters or when the fault is triggered;

- the formation of a database regarding the operation of the hydro aggregate.

The computer monitor displays dynamically and in real time the state of the hydro aggregate, as well as the values of the main functional parameters. The communication status with the programmable controller and the electronic meters is also monitored.

Also, the central computing unit provides information in the form of images that appear on the central unit's monitor and are called "synoptic panels". The algorithm for accessing the synoptic panels within the main field is shown symbolically in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Algorithm for accessing synoptic tables [3]

Conclusions

By automating a hydropower plant, a safety contribution to operation will be obtained; a high operational reliability; a reduction in maintenance costs; as well as maximizing the production of electricity.

Using relatively low financial resources, the automation installations can be modernized, the effect being the significant increase in the performance of the entire hydroelectric plant.

The future belongs to the hydropower plants automatically controlled by the automate systems based on the modern computational technique [6].

The work performed at HPP Leșu is a an example of good practice in the hydropower field, and represents a success from the technical point of view.

Acknowledgement

This work was carried out through the Core Program within the National Research Development and Innovation Plan 2022-2027, carried out with the support of MCID, project no. PN 23140103.

References

1. <http://www.schneider-electric.com/medias/solutions/downloads/280smallhydro-power-plant,v1.pdf>
2. Punys P., Dumbrasukas A., Kvaraciejus A., Vyciene G. Tools for small hydropower plant resource planning and development: A review of technology and applications. *Energies* 2011, 4, 1258–1277
3. ICEMENERG. Soluție modernă de conducere, în concepție centralizată, a unei hidrocentrale cu amplasament izolat. Aplicație practică la CHE Lesu (3,4 MW). Ctr nr. 99/2011
4. A catalog on I & C for Automation on "Hydro advancement project (HAP)" prepared for U.S. Department of Energy, under contact DE-AC05-00OR22725, 2011
5. Ullah K., Basit A., Ullah Z., Aslam S. Automatic Generation Control Strategies in Conventional and Modern Power Systems: A Comprehensive Overview. *Energies* 2021, 14(9), 2376, 2021
6. Aksoy B. Estimation of energy produced in hydroelectric power plant industrial automation using deep learning and hybrid machine learning techniques. *Electro Power Components and Systems* 2021, 49, 213–232